

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Sumarah, D. J., Pawito, & Naini, A. M. I. (2023). Engagement Declining on Indonesian Customs Instagram: A Content Analysis of Visual Factor. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 6(1), 81-93.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.06.01.395

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Engagement Declining on Indonesian Customs Instagram: A Content Analysis of Visual Factor

Darmadi Joko Sumarah¹, Pawito², Albert Muhammad Isrun Naini³

^{1,2} Magister of Communication Program, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Sebelas Maret University, Indonesia

³ Research Center for Area Studies, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN)

Correspondence: Darmadi Joko Sumarah. Email: darmadi.joko@student.uns.ac.id

Abstract

Government social media offers potential as a means of communicating with the public in new, responsive, and exciting ways. Social media, especially Instagram, is starting to be used widely by the government to communicate with citizens. Unfortunately, the majority of government social media get low user engagement. Indonesian customs as a government agency sustained a significant shift in communicating through Instagram social media. This study aims to find the factors that make the difference in this phenomenon and the combination of visual codes that provide the highest engagement. A quantitative content analysis framework is used to analyze posts shared on social media. Posts converted into data form are then analyzed using statistical analysis. This study found that an engagement trend and visual factor strategy shifted on Indonesia Customs Instagram during the observation period. The results of this study are that content type, visual aesthetics, and presentation modality significantly differ from the average engagement of Indonesian Customs on Instagram. Changes in engagement occur due to changes in the combination of visual factors. Informational content type, expressive aesthetics, and lean modality in government social media posts provide the highest engagement than the combination of other variable codes. Public needs and interest in government social media are necessary to be considered for future development and management. Government social media can be an effective means of communication if it is used with a two-way communication approach between the government and the public.

Keywords: Government Social Media, Content Type, Visual Aesthetics, Presentation Modality, Engagement

1. Introduction

More than half of the world's population are active users of social media based on We are Social data in February 2022. Moreover, in Indonesia, active users of social media reach 161 million users (68.9%) of the total population. The WhatsApp application is ranked first as the most frequently used social media in Indonesia, followed by Instagram in the second and Facebook in the third. This situation shows that social media has become part of Indonesian society (Kepios, n.d.). Spotting this situation, it is natural for the government to start using social media for various purposes related to the wider community. Social media can be used to determine the development of a topic as consideration for the policy-making process (Lawelai & Sadat, 2022) and to communicate with the public

(Chatfield & Reddick, 2018). In its development, government social media (GSM) began to be used to establish open communication (Bonsón et al., 2019) and public interaction and satisfaction as the leading indicator of its success (Rahayuningsih et al., 2018; Sari, 2021; Subhan, 2016; Wahyudianto, 2015).

Media content is crucial in exhibiting the government's performance towards stakeholders (Nurhaeni et al., 2021). GSM has more diversity of content than commercial social media, which can increase public engagement (Rietveld et al., 2020). GSM content, mainly information and news, can be shown in infographics to increase user interest in the report (Amit-Danhi & Shifman, 2022). The government can communicate more relaxed through social media by prioritizing user responses, especially on Instagram (Gruzd et al., 2018). Forming characteristics, labeling agencies, appointing togetherness, and seeking a collective agreement can be powerful strategies (Djuyandi, 2017). Establishing a communication mechanism whereby the Government can take appropriate roles when dealing with other stakeholders is a critical point in achieving program objectives (Abdurahman, 2017). Unfortunately, Political intervention makes the formation of communication policies that are not aligned and tend to be biased (Sirait, 2021). The government still focuses on technical matters rather than more strategic things (Rosalina, 2021). GSM is still not fully utilized, and sometimes it is only used as a means of reporting (Neely & Collins, 2018). Participatory communication within the Government of Indonesia also appears to be low in certain areas (Aminah, 2016).

As a government agency, Indonesian Customs also adopt social media as a communication channel with the public. Indonesian Customs uses various social media platforms, including Youtube, Twitter, TikTok, Instagram, and Facebook. Followers on these social media platforms are pretty high, with 25.2 thousand on Youtube, 35.5 thousand on Twitter, 43.1 thousand on TikTok, 124 thousand on Instagram, and 276 thousand on Facebook. Through each social media, Indonesian Customs is active in providing public information. High engagement with users on each post is the primary goal of the communication strategy implemented. Indonesian Customs has had an escalation trend of engagement since the use of social media Instagram in 2015. Unfortunately, this trend broke even decreased significantly in 2021, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Engagement trend on Indonesia customs Instagram

Instagram is one of the social media platforms that emphasize visual appearance to encourage the use of its application (Aljukhadar et al., 2020). An attractive visual display can facilitate users' interaction on social media, which underlies engagement (Bhandari et al., 2019). A stunning visual appearance of a post is built on several main factors, namely content type, visual aesthetics, and presentation (Barreto & Ramalho, 2019); (Bhandari et al., 2019); (Huang et al., 2022). The content type is the topic of the message conveyed in a post that leads to a discussion category (Chen et al., 2020). Visual aesthetics is an innovative factor related to the form of message

form aimed at attracting users' attention (Greussing & Boomgaarden, 2019). Presentation modality relates to the interface format used to convey various signs of communication in a post (Burgoon et al., 2002).

Research on government use of social media is scarce. Several studies revolve around the use of virtual space (Gintova, 2019), the interaction between the public and the government (Chen et al., 2020), the categorization of the content topic (DePaula et al., 2018), and challenges faced on implementing process (Dekker et al., 2020). At the same time, research on visual factors closely related to the level of engagement on government social media is sparse (Dolan et al., 2019).

This study aims to analyze the phenomenon of the decline in the level of public engagement of the Indonesian customs Instagram account in terms of visual factor analysis. This study aims to find visual post factors and the right strategy to get the highest engagement on posts on the Indonesian Customs Instagram account.

RQ1. What factors make the difference in the level of engagement in the Indonesian Customs Instagram post?

RQ2. Which code combination gets the highest engagement in the Indonesian Customs Instagram post?

In the context of social media, engagement is a form of user interaction with the post, including consuming, liking, sharing, and commenting (Dolan et al., 2019). Engagement is often used to measure success in running social media (Peñaflor, 2018). The number of likes, comments, and sharing or retweets indicates engagement (Chen et al., 2020). The concept and method of measuring engagement are still in the stage of continuous research and do not yet have a final idea (Dolan et al., 2019); (Yavetz & Aharony, 2021); (Kostyk & Huhmann, 2021); (Testa et al., 2020); (Peñaflor, 2018). In this study, engagement on social media Instagram is seen from users' liking and commenting behaviour. User interaction can be seen from a post's number of likes and comments.

Content types on government social media posts are dominated by informational and symbolic messages (condolences, happy birthdays, religious holidays, and other non-political messages) (DePaula et al., 2018). The existing literature states that content types that trigger emotional factors tend to have high engagement (Joo et al., 2018; Soares et al., 2022). Meanwhile, self-oriented messages have the weakest engagement (Kusumasondjaja, 2018).

Based on the uses and gratification theory, consuming content from government social media account posts is based on the user's taste (Katz et al., 1974). The information needed by the community includes information related to services, new provisions, and activities of government agencies (Yavetz & Aharony, 2021). Therefore, posts containing information about a program or new provisions are classified with the information code. In contrast, posts containing information related to the activities and achievements of the agency (self-oriented content) are organized with the achievement code. Thus, posts on government social media accounts with information content will get higher engagement.

H1. Posts in the information code will get higher engagement on Indonesian Customs Instagram.

Visual aesthetics in social media is the overall beauty that includes the quality of images of people and objects that inspire and are easy to store and share (Aljukhadar et al., 2020). Visual aesthetics assessment in social media is done by classifying it into two aesthetic segments, namely classical and expressive (Bhandari et al., 2019; Kusumasondjaja, 2018; Marmat, 2022). Posts are classified in classical aesthetics if they use a simple, symmetrical, orderly, and precise arrangement pattern. Meanwhile, posts are classified as expressive aesthetics when they use complex patterns, special visual effects, various color combinations, and unique patterns (Bhandari et al., 2019; Marmat, 2022).

Visual aesthetics in social media is often associated with prominent beauty, being able to inspire and generate a desire to interact (Aljukhadar et al., 2020). Therefore, this study argues that expressive aesthetics has a more significant influence than classical aesthetics when posts are delivered in media that prioritizes visualization characteristics. That way, posts on government social media accounts on the Instagram platform will get higher engagement when using expressive aesthetics.

H2. Post that is displayed with expressive aesthetics will get higher engagement on Indonesian Customs Instagram

Presentation modality is a method for conveying messages using various forms of communication, which can be a combination of verbal, visual, or audio (Burgoon et al., 2002). Modalities in Instagram media can be seen at the level of content visualization, where posts can be categorized into 2 (two) types of modality, namely lean modality and rich modality. Lean modality is used for posts with only one visualization mode, such as static visual content or photos. At the same time, Rich modality is used for posts that use multimodal visualizations such as audio-visual or video (Kusumasondjaja, 2020).

The emergence of various social media platforms brings different post characteristics for each. The types of posts on social media can be categorized into 3 (three) groups: text only, images, or videos. Text posts only have one modality, so they are classified as the lowest media richness. In contrast, video is included in the Rich modality because it has various modalities, such as audio and visual (Chen et al., 2020; Denктаş-Şakar & Sürücü, 2020; Yue et al., 2019). There are still disagreements about the effect of presentation modality in the context of public interaction with government social media accounts (Chen et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2022) (Zhang et al., 2022). This study argues that presentation modality has a negative effect on engagement levels. This is based on the description above and 3 (three) assumptions, namely 1) the public is more concerned with whether government social media accounts can provide accurate and appropriate information. 2) High modality results in incomplete information (Chen et al., 2020). 3) Media richness must be appropriate to the context and purpose to get the best results (Daft, 1985; Daft et al., 1987). That way, posts on government social media accounts on Instagram will get higher engagement when using the lean modality.

H3. Posts displayed with a lower modality will get higher engagement on Indonesian Customs Instagram.

2. Methods

This research is suitable for using the content analysis method because it can assess samples with a large number of characters and various types systematically and objectively. This method allows researchers to analyze forms of communication and interaction freely (Neuendorf, 2017). Content analysis has become a popular framework used in research on social media (Chen et al., 2020; Denктаş-Şakar & Sürücü, 2020; DePaula et al., 2018; Joo et al., 2018; Lappas et al., 2018; Yue et al., 2019) (Kusumasondjaja, 2018; Peñafior, 2018).

The first stage of data collection is to find the Indonesian Customs Instagram account on the Instagram platform. The Instagram account @beacukai with a blue checkmark is interpreted as the official Instagram account of Indonesian Customs. Data samples were taken from all posts on the @beacukai account between January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2021. Data collection was carried out in March 2022. Post and reels were taken as data in this study. The engagement indicators taken are the number of likes and comments.

This study used 3 (three) code groups, namely content type, visual aesthetic, and presentation modality. The content type code group was formed by researchers using systematic steps based on previous research (Kusumasondjaja, 2018). At the same time, the visual aesthetic and presentation modality code groups use codes used in previous studies (Bhandari et al., 2019; Kusumasondjaja, 2020; Maity et al., 2018; Marmat, 2022). The code shown in table 1 is used to categorize research data.

Table 1: Definition of Operational Variable

Variabel	Klasifikasi	Definisi Operasional
<i>Content type</i>	<i>Symbolic Message</i>	Instagram posts contain symbolic messages to express congratulations or condolences on national holidays, religious holidays, holidays of other agencies, and other statements containing commemorations or greetings.
	<i>Information</i>	Instagram posts containing information related to regulations, programs, and technical procedures for new services in the field of customs and excise.

		Information codes are used to classify posts oriented towards enhancing user insight.
	<i>Achievement</i>	Instagram posts containing activities with direct involvement of customs specifically mention the activities, location, and results of these activities that have been carried out from the perpetrator's perspective (Self-oriented message).
<i>Visual Aesthetic</i>	<i>Classical Aesthetics</i>	Instagram posts that use one or more objects with general symmetry or orientation with a more straightforward pattern.
	<i>Expressive Aesthetics</i>	Instagram posts that use many asymmetrical objects or unusual appearances using multiple patterns or colors.
<i>Presentation modality</i>	<i>Lean Modality</i>	Instagram posts that are submitted in one visual format (static image).
	<i>Rich Modality</i>	Instagram posts that are submitted in several visual formats (Audio-visual, video).

After the research data were collected, the outlier test was carried out to determine the extreme data from the independent and dependent variables to avoid a later bias in the research results (Dao et al., 2021). This outlier test uses the z-score method, where data with a value range outside ± 3.29 is entered into the outlier data and will be excluded (Mowbray et al., 2019). The next stage of data processing is to test the normality of the data using the Kolmogorov Smirnov One Sample Test. Data is categorized as normally distributed if the significance value exceeds 0.005 (del Barrio et al., 2020). The data were tested for homogeneity to know the level/rank of the data with the variance of the range predictor variable using the Levene test. The results of this Levene test will affect the method of further analysis (Y. J. Kim & Cribbie, 2018).

To determine the ranking of data with continuous or ordinal type, the Kruskal-Wallis test was carried out to see the difference between independent variables (2 or more variables) in a dependent variable to test the hypothesis of this study (Johnson, 2022). The Post Hoc test was carried out in terms of the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test, stating that there were differences in the content type variables. This follow-up test uses the Dunnett-C test because the number of research samples is quite large.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Result

Content analysis on Instagram produces data of 577 posts from January 1, 2020, to December 31, 2021. This indicates that Indonesian Customs and Excise, on average, posts 24 posts per month on Instagram accounts. The data is then analyzed using the content analysis method based on three predetermined variables.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the content type variable

		Content type			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Symbolic Message	101	17.5	17.5	17.5
	Information	270	46.8	46.8	64.3
	Achievement	206	35.7	35.7	100.0
	Total	577	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 2. The research data was analyzed with the content type variable with detailed analysis results, namely posts of Symbolic Message codes as many as 101 posts (17.5%), Information as many as 270 posts (46.8%), and Achievement as many as 206 posts (35.7 posts). %).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of the visual aesthetics variables

Visual Aesthetics					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Classical Aesthetic	105	18.2	18.2	18.2
	Expressive Aesthetic	472	81.8	81.8	100.0
	Total	577	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 3, content analysis with Visual Aesthetics variables found that 105 posts (18.2%) used Classical Aesthetics while 472 posts (81.8%) used Expressive Aesthetics.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Presentation Modality

Presentation modality					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Lean modality	479	83.0	83.0	83.0
	Rich modality	98	17.0	17.0	100.0
	Total	577	100.0	100.0	

As shown in Table 4, the Presentation modality variable found that as many as 479 posts (83%) used the Lean modality and as many as 98 posts (17%) used the Rich modality.

Table 5: Distribution of Variables

Distribution of Variables				
		2020	2021	Selisih
Variable	Kategori	Frequency	Frequency	(%)
Engagement	Sum of Like	864.930	380.758	-55,9
	Sum of Comment	17.404	7.243	-58,3
Post	Sum of Post	319	258	-19,1
Content type	Symbolic Message	56	45	-19,6
	Information	191	79	-58,6
	Achievement	72	134	+86,1
Visual Aesthetic	Classical	0	105	+100
	Expressive	319	153	-52
Presentation modality	Lean	271	208	-23
	Rich	48	50	-4,1

Based on Table 5, there was a significant decrease in engagement from 2020, which was 55.9% in the number of likes and 58.3% in the number of comments. Changes occurred in the content type variable, where posts with the Information code decreased by 58.6% while posts with the achievement code increased by 86.1% from the previous year. Changes also occurred in the visual aesthetics variable, where classical aesthetics began to be applied starting in 2021 with a fairly flat portion with expressive aesthetics of 52%.

The outlier test removed eight extreme data from the advanced analysis stage in this study so that the amount of data that could be used for further analysis was 569 data. The extreme data is data with the number of likes that is too high than the average number of likes (Average 2,158 likes/post).

Based on the normality test result using the one sample Kolmogorov Smirnov, the significance value is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.005. This indicates that the data in this study are not normally distributed. Based on the Levene homogeneity test, The content type and visual aesthetics variable have a Heterogeneous data distribution because the significance value of both variables on engagement is 0.000 (less than 0.005) while the presentation

modality variable has homogeneous data distribution with a significance value at 0.363 (more significant than 0.005). Because there are heterogeneous distributed data on some of the variables, the research data is categorized as Heterogeneous distributed data.

Because the data has an abnormal distribution and is of heterogeneous type, the Kruskal-Wallis test is used to perform further analysis. The Kruskal-Wallis test was carried out in stages from the independent variables to the dependent variable.

Table 6: The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test for content type variables on engagement

Kruskal-Wallis Test			
Rank			
	Content type	N	Mean Rank
Engagement	Symbolic Message	101	226.22
	Information	263	305.34
	Achievement	205	287.86
	Total	569	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
	Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	16.999
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variabel : <i>content type</i>	

Based on the table 6, the significance value is .000, which is less than 0.005. This test gives the result that there is a significant difference between the average engagement with the Post Type Variable. Because the post-type variable consists of more than two codes and there is a difference in the average engagement, further tests need to be carried out using the Dunnett C test.

Table 7: Further test results with Dunnett-C

Post Hoc Test					
Multiple Comparison					
Dependent Variable: Engagement					
Dunnett C					
(I) content type	(J) content type	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Symbolic Message	Information	-624.6681*	181.75234	-1055.7810	-193.5551
	Achievement	-218.12572	170.42794	-622.8766	186.6252
Information	Symbolic Message	624.66807*	181.75234	193.5551	1055.7810
	Achievement	406.54235*	132.01930	95.1628	717.9219
Achievement	Symbolic Message	218.12572	170.42794	-186.6252	622.8766
	Information	-406.5424*	132.01930	-717.9219	-95.1628

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Based on table 7, it can be seen that the Information code content type has the highest difference in the level of engagement, with a mean difference value of 624,66807 against the Symbolic Message code and with a mean

difference value of 406,54235 against the Achievement code. Therefore, H1, which states that Indonesian Customs Instagram content in the form of information will get higher engagement, is acceptable.

Table 8. Kruskal-Wallis Test Results Visual Aesthetic Variables on Engagement

Kruskal-Wallis Test			
Rank			
	Visual Aesthetics	N	Mean Rank
Engagement	Classical	104	253.90
	Expressive	465	291.96
	Total	569	

Test Statistics^{a,b}	
	Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	4.554
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.033
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: Visual Aesthetics	

Based on Table 8, the significance value is .033, which is less than 0.005. This test gives the result that there is a significant difference between the average engagement with the Visual Aesthetics Variable. Based on the mean rank value, it can be seen that expressive aesthetics has a higher average engagement value than classical aesthetics. Therefore, H2 states that Indonesian Customs Instagram content displayed with expressive aesthetics will get higher engagement is acceptable.

Table 9: Kruskal-Wallis Test Results Presentation modality variable on engagement

Kruskal-Wallis Test			
Rank			
	Presentation modality	N	Mean Rank
Engagement	Lean	471	305.82
	Rich	98	184.92
	Total	569	

Test Statistics^{a,b}	
	Engagement
Kruskal-Wallis H	43.875
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.000
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: Visual Aesthetics	

Based on Table 9, the significance value is .000, which is less than 0.005. This test gives the result that there is a significant difference between the average engagement with the Presentation modality variable. Based on the mean rank value, it can be seen that the lean modality has a higher average value of engagement than the rich modality. Therefore, H3, which states that Indonesian Customs Instagram content displayed with a lower modality will get higher engagement is acceptable.

3.2 Discussion

Overall in the content type variable, the posts with the Information code got the largest portion (46.8%), slightly different from the Achievement code (35.7%). In comparison, the Symbolic Message code got the smallest percentage (17.5%). Most posts use expressive aesthetics (81.8%) rather than classical aesthetics (18.2%). At the

same time, the presentation modality is dominated by lean modality (83%) rather than rich modality (17%). From the analysis of descriptive statistical data, it can be seen that posts are dominated by using a combination of Information and achievement topic codes and expressive aesthetics through lean modality.

Based on the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test, it can be seen that there is a significant difference between the average engagement in the content type variable. These results were then analyzed further by using Dunnett C post Hoc Test to obtain a ranking order. The follow-up test found that posts with information topics will positively affect getting the highest engagement. Posts with the topic of achievement and symbolic messages also positively influence engagement but at a lower level. As for the visual aesthetics variable, it is evident that expressive aesthetics significantly positively impact the level of engagement. Likewise, the Presentation modality variable clearly shows that the Lean modality significantly positively affects the level of engagement.

The results of this study state that the information code gets the highest average engagement rank than the achievement code and symbolic message. This means that the public tends to interact more with posts containing information on provisions or regulations related to the agency field. This result is in accordance with previous research, which stated that posts containing helpful information for the community would get more attention (Yavetz & Aharony, 2021).

This reinforces that public interaction with government social media is based on community subjectivity related to expectations and fulfillment of the information submitted. Indonesian Customs Instagram posts oriented towards increasing user insight (regulations, programs, new technical service procedures) in the field of customs and excise have been proven to facilitate higher public interaction than posts on other topics.

Posts that use expressive aesthetics get a higher average engagement than those that use classical aesthetics. This means that people prefer to interact with posts with asymmetric objects or unusual appearances that use several patterns or colors than posts that use one or more objects with general symmetry or orientation with simpler designs. This result is also in accordance with previous research that states the same (Bhandari et al., 2019; Kusumasondjaja, 2020).

Social media that prioritizes visualization displays will build a tendency toward beauty with an asymmetric orientation, the use of various colors that will produce an unusual visualization. In the Indonesian Customs Instagram, posts that use exceptional concepts, irregular patterns, and multiple colors are proven to attract people's attention to interact.

Meanwhile, the lean modality code gets a higher average engagement in the presentation modality variable than the rich modality. This means that people tend to interact more with posts displayed in one visual format (image) than posts delivered in several visual formats (audio-visual, video). This is in accordance with previous research, which states that media richness has a negative effect on engagement in the context of information seeking (Chen et al., 2020).

Community interaction with government social media aims to fulfill information so that posts that can display it more fully will get more interaction. Using lean modality will reduce the evaporation of information caused by multiple modalities. Indonesian Customs Instagram posts displayed in one visualization format (static image) are proven to get higher interactions than posts that use several visualization formats.

There was a change in the use of code combinations on Indonesian Customs Instagram during the research period. This can be seen in the descriptive statistical analysis, which illustrates that in 2020 posts are dominated by content type code information, the use of expressive aesthetics, and posts displayed in lean modality. Meanwhile, in 2021 there will be a change in the combination where the content type achievement type begins to dominate, the use of classical and expressive aesthetics is balanced, and posts are still consistently displayed in lean modality.

Based on the results of the research that has been done, the change in the combination is a factor that causes a decrease in the level of engagement. In 2020, the variety of codes used was information-expressive-lean, so it can

be analyzed that the Information (High Rank) code coupled with Expressive Aesthetics (High Rank) and with Lean modality (High Rank) will have a positive effect on maximum engagement levels. Meanwhile, in 2021, the code combination will change to achievement-classical/expressive-lean so that the analysis that appears is the achievement code (Medium Rank) combined with Classical (Low Rank) and Expressive aesthetics (High rank), which is presented in the Lean modality (High Rank) will have a positive influence on the level of engagement but not maximal.

4. Conclusion

Social media, as a means of communication that is cheap and has a broad reach, makes it a massive interaction channel used by the people of Indonesia. As one of the government agencies, Indonesian Customs is the primary source of information on issues related to handling imported and exported goods. Through the Instagram account @beacukai, every post by Beacukai Indonesia can reach as many as 125 thousand followers. This makes the Instagram platform one of the leading digital communication tools for interacting with the public. Indonesian Customs has had an increasing trend of engagement since the use of social media Instagram in 2015. Unfortunately, this trend of increasing engagement stopped and decreased significantly in 2021. What factors contributed to the difference in the level of engagement? What code do combinations get the most engagement? The content type is the main factor that makes a difference in changes in the level of engagement in the Indonesian Customs Instagram account. The visual factors that contributed to the difference in the change in the level of engagement were visual aesthetics and presentation modality. At the same time, the combination of codes from these factors that gives the highest level of engagement is the use of information topics in content type, expressive use in visual aesthetics, and appearance using lean modality in presentation modality. This change in the combination of visual factors will provide a difference in the average post engagement, ultimately making a difference in the overall engagement level.

Practically, the results of this study can be considered in efforts to increase the level of engagement on the Instagram platform by Indonesian Customs and other government agencies. Based on the Use and Gratification theory, people in consuming media exposure prioritize self-satisfaction as the goal of the consumption behaviour. To get a high level of engagement, GSM management and development should pay attention to the needs and interests of the community. This research is focused on the Indonesian Customs Instagram account, so it does not have a significant theoretical contribution. More in-depth analysis of public needs and interest in government social media needs to be done to get a more balanced view from both sides.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank The Ministry of Communication and Information especially for supporting this research work. The author would like to thank everyone who participated in the study, helped with data collecting, and provided insightful feedback, especially the editors and reviewers so that this publication could be published appropriately.

References

- Abdurahman, B. (2017). Authoritative Agency for Tourism Zone: An Innovative Instrument for Destination Development? *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 9(1), 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.09.2017.15-27>
- Aljukhadar, M., Bériault Poirier, A., & Senecal, S. (2020). Imagery makes social media captivating! Aesthetic value in a consumer-as-value-maximizer framework. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 14(3), 285–303. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-10-2018-0136>
- Aminah, S. (2016). The Application of Participatory Communication in the Implementation of Small Farmers Empowerment Program. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 8(1), 135–148. <http://jurnal.kemendagri.go.id/index.php/jbp/index>
- Amit-Danhi, E. R., & Shifman, L. (2022). Off the charts: user engagement enhancers in election infographics. *Information Communication and Society*, 25(1), 55–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2020.1761858>
- Barreto, A. M., & Ramalho, D. (2019). The impact of involvement on engagement with brand posts. *Journal of*

- Research in Interactive Marketing*, 13(3), 277–301. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-01-2018-0013>
- Bhandari, U., Chang, K., & Neben, T. (2019). Understanding the impact of perceived visual aesthetics on user evaluations: An emotional perspective. *Information and Management*, 56(1), 85–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2018.07.003>
- Bonsón, E., Perea, D., & Bednárová, M. (2019). Twitter as a tool for citizen engagement: An empirical study of the Andalusian municipalities. *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(3), 480–489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.03.001>
- Burgoon, J. K., Bonito, J. A., Ramirez, A. J., Dunbar, N. E., Kam, K., & Fischer, J. (2002). Testing the interactivity principle: Effects of mediation, propinquity, and verbal and nonverbal modalities in interpersonal interaction. *Journal of Communication*, 52(3), 657–677. <https://doi.org/10.1093/joc/52.3.657>
- Chatfield, A. T., & Reddick, C. G. (2018). The role of policy entrepreneurs in open government data policy innovation diffusion: An analysis of Australian Federal and State Governments. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(1), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.10.004>
- Chen, Q., Min, C., Zhang, W., Wang, G., Ma, X., & Evans, R. (2020). Unpacking the black box: How to promote citizen engagement through government social media during the COVID-19 crisis. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 110(April), 106380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106380>
- Daft, R. L. (1985). A proposed integration among organization information requirements, media richness and structural design. *Office of Naval Research Technical Report Series*.
- Daft, R. L., Lengel, R. H., & Trevino, L. K. (1987). Message equivocality, media selection, and manager performance: Implications for information systems. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 11(3), 355–366. <https://doi.org/10.2307/248682>
- Dao, P. D., Mantripragada, K., He, Y., & Qureshi, F. Z. (2021). Improving hyperspectral image segmentation by applying inverse noise weighting and outlier removal for optimal scale selection. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 171(June 2020), 348–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2020.11.013>
- Dekker, R., van den Brink, P., & Meijer, A. (2020). Social media adoption in the police: Barriers and strategies. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.101441>
- Del Barrio, E., Inouzhe, H., & Matrán, C. (2020). On approximate validation of models: a Kolmogorov–Smirnov-based approach. *Test*, 29(4), 938–965. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11749-019-00691-1>
- Denktaş-Şakar, G., & Sürücü, E. (2020). Stakeholder engagement via social media: an analysis of third-party logistics companies. *Service Industries Journal*, 40(11–12), 866–889. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2018.1561874>
- DePaula, N., Dincelli, E., & Harrison, T. M. (2018). Toward a typology of government social media communication: Democratic goals, symbolic acts and self-presentation. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(1), 98–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.10.003>
- Djuyandi, Y. (2017). Political Communication Strategy of the Regional Head in Managing Government in North Gorontalo Regency. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 9(1), 53–61. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.09.2017.53-61>
- Dolan, R., Conduit, J., Frethey-Bentham, C., Fahy, J., & Goodman, S. (2019). Social media engagement behavior: A framework for engaging customers through social media content. *European Journal of Marketing*, 53(10), 2213–2243. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-03-2017-0182>
- Gintova, M. (2019). Understanding government social media users: an analysis of interactions on Immigration, Refugees and Citizenship Canada Twitter and Facebook. *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(4), 101388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.06.005>
- Greussing, E., & Boomgaarden, H. G. (2019). Simply Bells and Whistles?: Cognitive Effects of Visual Aesthetics in Digital Longforms. *Digital Journalism*, 7(2), 273–293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2018.1488598>
- Gruzd, A., Lannigan, J., & Quigley, K. (2018). Examining government cross-platform engagement in social media: Instagram vs Twitter and the big lift project. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35(4), 579–587. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2018.09.005>
- Huang, F., Chen, Q., Ma, W., & Evans, R. (2022). Promoting public engagement with household waste separation through government social media: A case study of Shanghai. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 320(May), 115825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115825>
- Johnson, R. W. (2022). Alternate Forms of the One-Way ANOVA F and Kruskal–Wallis Test Statistics. *Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education*, 30(1), 82–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26939169.2021.2025177>
- Joo, S., Choi, N., & Baek, T. H. (2018). Library marketing via social media: The relationships between Facebook content and user engagement in public libraries. *Online Information Review*, 42(6), 940–955. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-10-2017-0288>
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1974). Utilization of Mass Communication by the Individual. In J. G. Blumler, & E. Katz (Eds.). *The Uses of Mass Communications: Current Perspectives on Gratifications Research*, 37(4), 19–32.
- Kepios. (n.d.). *Digital 2022 Indonesia*. Retrieved April 23, 2022, from <https://datareportal.com/digital-indonesia>

- Kim, Y. J., & Cribbie, R. A. (2018). ANOVA and the variance homogeneity assumption: Exploring a better gatekeeper. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 71(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bmsp.12103>
- Kostyk, A., & Huhmann, B. A. (2021). Perfect social media image posts: symmetry and contrast influence consumer response. *European Journal of Marketing*, 55(6), 1747–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-09-2018-0629>
- Kusumasondjaja, S. (2018). The roles of message appeals and orientation on social media brand communication effectiveness: An evidence from Indonesia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 30(4), 1135–1158. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-10-2017-0267>
- Kusumasondjaja, S. (2020). Exploring the role of visual aesthetics and presentation modality in luxury fashion brand communication on Instagram. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 24(1), 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-02-2019-0019>
- Lappas, G., Triantafillidou, A., Deligiaouri, A., & Kleftodimos, A. (2018). Facebook Content Strategies and Citizens' Online Engagement: The Case of Greek Local Governments. *The Review of Socionetwork Strategies*, 12(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12626-018-0017-6>
- Lawelai, H., & Sadat, A. (2022). Trend Analysis of Positive Sentiment for Special Autonomy for Papua on Twitter. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 14(2), 213–224. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.14.2022.213-224>
- Maity, M., Dass, M., & Kumar, P. (2018). The impact of media richness on consumer information search and choice. *Journal of Business Research*, 87(February), 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.02.003>
- Marmat, G. (2022). Influence of aesthetics attributes of brand Web pages on customer brand engagement. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-07-2021-0126>
- Mowbray, F. I., Fox-wasylyshyn, S. M., & El-masri, M. M. (2019). Univariate Outliers : A Conceptual Overview for the Nurse Researcher. *Sage Research Methods*, 51(1), 31–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0844562118786647>
- Neely, S. R., & Collins, M. (2018). Social Media and Crisis Communications: A Survey of Local Governments in Florida. *Journal of Homeland Security and Emergency Management*, 15(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jhsem-2016-0067>
- Neuendorf, K. (2017). *The Content Analysis Guidebook*. In SAGE (Second Edi). Thousand Oaks. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11589-998-0087-6>
- Nurhaeni, I. D. A., Anggreni, L. S., Kusumawati, N. S., Permitasari, D., & Putri, I. S. (2021). Internationalization of Higher Education: A Case Study on Media Utilization, Policies Consistency and Stakeholders' Insights in Indonesia. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 13(2), 207–218. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.13.2021.207-218>
- Peñaflor, J. (2018). Beyond “Likes”: An assessment of user engagement in Facebook among Philippine academic libraries. *Library Management*, 39(1–2), 59–65. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-12-2016-0100>
- Rahayuningsih, Y., Anggraini, Y., & Listyaningsih, L. (2018). Implementation Quality Level of Health Public Service Policy in Banten Province Local Hospital (RSUD). *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 10(1), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.10.2018.121-134>
- Rietveld, R., van Dolen, W., Mazloom, M., & Worrying, M. (2020). What You Feel, Is What You Like Influence of Message Appeals on Customer Engagement on Instagram. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 49, 20–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2019.06.003>
- Rosalina, I. F. (2021). Media Relations in Implementing Law No. 2 of 2018 on MD3. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 171–182. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.13.2021.171-182>
- Sari, N. M. (2021). Information Service Activities on the Public Satisfaction Levels in the Public Service Mall of Palopo City. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 13(2), 219–229. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.13.2021.219-229>
- Sirait, F. E. T. (2021). Policy Communication and the Solidity of the Jokowi's Second Term Coalition in Handling Covid-19. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 13(2), 257–268. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.13.2021.257-268>
- Soares, J. C., Limongi, R., & Cohen, E. D. (2022). Engagement in a social media: an analysis in higher education institutions. *Online Information Review*, 46(2), 256–284. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OIR-06-2020-0242>
- Subhan, A. (2016). Multidirectional Networks of Government Transparency: A Preliminary Model. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 8(2), 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.21787/jbp.08.2016.209-219>
- Testa, D. S., Bakhshian, S., & Eike, R. (2020). Engaging consumers with sustainable fashion on Instagram. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 25(4), 569–584. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-11-2019-0266>
- Wahyudianto, H. (2015). MEASUREMENT OF SATISFACTION SOCIETY POLICY IMPLEMENTATION OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 7(4), 331–346.
- Yavetz, G., & Aharony, N. (2021). Social media for government information dissemination: content, characteristics and civic engagement. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 73(3), 473–496. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-07-2020-0201>
- Yue, C. A., Thelen, P., Robinson, K., & Men, L. R. (2019). How do CEOs communicate on Twitter? A comparative study between Fortune 200 companies and top startup companies. *Corporate Communications*, 24(3), 532–552. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CCIJ-03-2019-0031>
- Zhang, W., Yuan, H., Zhu, C., Chen, Q., & Evans, R. (2022). Does Citizen Engagement With Government Social Media Accounts Differ During the Different Stages of Public Health Crises? An Empirical Examination of

the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10(June), 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.807459>